

Data Stewardship Wizard

Import and Export and

FAIR Implementation Profiles

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This hackathon team worked on improvements to the [Data Stewardship Wizard](#) (DSW). In particular, we focused on enabling import and export of maDMPs as well as adding elements supporting FAIR implementation profiles.

Import

Currently, DSW has no feature related to questionnaire nor DMP “import” but it is necessary for interoperability between tools using maDMPs. This Issue (same as the export of maDMP in the section below) targets the implementation of a prototype of maDMP import as a pre-filled starter questionnaire in DSW. As the Knowledge Model (KM) has already been adjusted and mapping with DCS made for export already, this task was pure programming. We implemented the feature on the frontend of the DSW, to allow a user select (or drag&drop) JSON maDMP files, the DSW then parses the file and extracts the relevant information in a permissive way (almost everything is optional), provides a preview to the user with extracted data and then allows to create a pre-filled questionnaire with contributors, projects (including funding), and datasets (including distributions and licences). We then tested this feature with exports from other tools such as DMPTool or with examples in the DCS repository. We plan to enhance and generalise the import feature for possibly other input formats and then release it as part of DSW. In Figure 1, we depict an overview of how the import feature for the DSW works.

Figure 1: Import of maDMPs into DSW.

Export

The DSW uses Jinja2 templates for DMP exports from questionnaires that are based on a certain knowledge model (KM). To allow export of maDMP in JSON according to the DCS, we defined two subtasks. First, extending and adjusting common KM to be more compliant. Second, creating a Jinja2 template for assembling JSON files from questionnaires. This Issue is essential for interoperability and using DMPs from DSW in other tools or transferring to different stakeholders, e.g., funders in the future. We achieved the adjustments in the KM rather easily thanks to the flexibility provided by DSW, e.g., there are multiple datasets, with possible multiple distributions, and each with multiple licences. We also implemented a template for exporting to JSON, compliant with the JSON-schema. Moreover, a template for exporting to RDF (DSW allows export in RDF/XML, TTL, N3, NT, JSON-LD, and TRIG) using DCSO has also been implemented. Finally, we also achieved automatic submission of maDMP from DSW to DMPTool via API, i.e., the user clicks a button, and DMP is loaded to DMPTool. For the future, we plan to increase the coverage of optional attributes (for distributions and cost), we will also deploy it to all of our DSW instances. In Figure 2, we depict an overview of the export feature in the DWS.

Figure 2: Export of maDMPs from DSW.

FAIR Implementation Profiles

[FAIR Implementation Profiles](#) (FIP) represent a list of technological choices a community makes for implementing FAIR. Those choices are, of course, essential for data management planning and should be reflected in DMPs. In this task, we explored how a mapping between questionnaires in DSW and FIPs should be done, in order to allow pre-filled questionnaires based on selected FIP to make filling DMPs (and therefore also maDMPs) easier for researchers. The mapping has been done, several questions related to FIPs have been added to common KM in DSW, and pre-filled DMPs are left for future work, but easily feasible now.